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OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Deliverable 4.3

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Deliverable Administration and Summary

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Work Programme Description	Three international workshops will take place: Lisbon (2013-14), Cottbus (2014-15) and Belgrade (2015-16). The workshops will address specific housing problems at community level. The themes of the workshops will be informed by the outcomes of the subnetworks' Housing Studies and Community Participation. The workshops will be integrated into the coordinated learning activities carried out at the seminars and courses at the participating institutions. Preparatory activities will be carried out as part of the joint learning activities developed in OIKODOMOS Workspaces. Both the process and the outcomes of the workshop will be documented in the network.				
Comments					

Document history

V	Date	Author	Description
1	2016-09-01	Mirjana Devetaković (AF-BELGRADE)	Document structure and first draft of contents
2	2017-02-19	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Final review and editing
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Three international workshops were planned within the OIKONET project to take place in Lisbon (2014), Cottbus (2015) and Belgrade (2016). The Belgrade workshop, took place from June 6 – 11, 2016, following the successful implementations of the workshops in Lisbon, in 2014, and Cottbus, in 2015. The theme of the workshop was “Renewing/Revitalizing. Creating Liveable Cities”. The case study focused on the issues around the development of the Belgrade waterfront, thus complementing the micro interventions in the Lisbon workshop “Formal/Informal” and the macro scale of the “Growth/Shrinkage” workshop in Cottbus/Berlin.

The Belgrade workshop brought together 58 students and 24 tutors, from 17 higher education institutions. In addition, members in charge of the pedagogic evaluation (WP6 Quality Assurance) were present in the workshop.

This workshop was dedicated to examining the strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies integrated architectural, urban design and urban planning issues in the creation a multifaceted framework to guide the development of liveable cities.

The area of study was Kosančićev Venac, a historical part of the city of Belgrade. It is a heterogeneous, mixed-use area connecting the Sava riverfront with the main pedestrian zone, next to the Kalemegdan fortress. Despite its excellent position and evident potential for revitalization, this area has been deteriorating for decades, losing part of its inhabitants and failing to attract new ones. Its predominant use is residential, although there are many educational and cultural institutions nearby.

The workshop was held in three stages, according to methodology already applied to previous workshops, which includes a preparatory stage carried out online, the workshop in Belgrade and the subsequent dissemination of the results.

The preparatory stage of the workshop was done entirely online, using **OIKODOMOS Workspaces**¹. At this stage the students received the necessary information about the selected site in Belgrade in various formats, as well as a selection of written references about liveable cities and regeneration strategies for contemporary cities.

For a less formal communication among participants, a Facebook group was created. This group has been the main Internet based communication channel during the realization of the workshop in Belgrade.

The activities carried out in one-week work in Belgrade included lectures, a guided historical walk around Kosančićev Venac, studio work, an interim critique and a final presentation. Along with these activities, there was a welcome meeting on the Belgrade waterfront the afternoon before the Workshop started, and a public presentation in the city the day after the workshop finalized.

¹ <http://www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/index.php/workshops/preview/31>

Two exhibitions were organized to support the workshop activities: an exhibition to showcase the work done during the preparatory stage, and a second one to display the proposals developed during the workshop.

In the preparatory stage, students were introduced to the various issues concerning urban regeneration. They also examined the area of study with the provided documentation, as well as all with information available in Internet (Google Maps and Street View). The results were documented in posters, which were displayed in an exhibition which was already installed as the workshop started.

As in the previous two workshops, the design studio work in Belgrade was done by mixed teams of students from various institutions. The teams made strategic proposals to intervene in Kosančićev Venac, at the micro, mezzo and macro scales. The presentation of final proposals was organized as a performance in which students acted as external experts in charge of the development of the area, some of the tutors acted as international investors from their respective countries, and other tutors played the role of the City of Belgrade government.

Apart from the official program, both tutors and students had a chance to socialize with their fellow colleagues from other countries, to strengthen professional contacts using social media, as well as to experience a vibrant life in Belgrade, one of the most popular cities of South-East Europe.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

This report summarizes the work done during the third international OIKONET workshop held in the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from June 6 - 11, 2016. It encompasses the preparatory activities done prior to the workshop in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environment, the program of activities and results produced in the workshop, the evaluation of the students' work by tutors and the activities to disseminate the workshop results. This report therefore provides a comprehensive view of the pedagogic work carried out on this workshop.

The main target groups are the tutors who participated in the workshop, as well as other faculty members from their home organizations who are involved in pedagogic innovation and contemporary housing. The report is also useful for faculty members at other institutions (mostly in architecture and urban planning), as it allows for a deeper insight into the work done in the OIKONET network to create a cross-disciplinary, trans-institutional pedagogical space about contemporary dwelling.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, was in charge of the organization of the workshop. 17 schools of architecture and planning (1 of them from a third country, Russia, and 1 of them from the subnetwork Community Participation) participated in the workshop activities, sending both tutors and students to Belgrade. The evaluation of the workshop activities has been conducted by USI. LA SALLE has edited this report. The coordination of the preparatory activities prior to the workshop was undertaken by LA SALLE, with the support of UTH, AAU and ITU.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The work carried out in the Belgrade workshop is very much related to the learning spaces being developed in the WP4 Pedagogical Activities. The learning space that was created to carry out these preparatory activities, under the title "Contemporary living patterns", is documented in Deliverable 4.1 "Learning spaces".

3 PROGRAM

The third OIKONET international workshop took place at the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from June 6 - 11, 2016. The workshop was dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies integrate architectural, urban design and urban planning issues to create a multifaceted framework to develop liveable cities.

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BELGRADE WORKSHOP JUNE 6-11, 2016

Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating liveable cities
FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE, SERBIA

The third OIKONET international workshop will take place at the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from 6th to 11th of June 2016. This workshop will be dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies will integrate architectural, urban design and urban planning issues to create a multifaceted framework to develop liveable cities.

The area of study is a Kosančićev Venac, a historical part of the city of Belgrade. It is a heterogeneous, mixed-use area connecting the Sava riverfront with the main pedestrian zone, next to the Kalemegdan fortress. Despite its excellent position and evident potential for revitalization, this area has been deteriorating for decades, losing part of its inhabitants and failing to attract new ones. Its predominant use is residential, although there are many institutions of education and culture nearby.

The workshop will provide a learning environment in which students and faculty members from schools of architecture from different countries in Europe will discuss a variety of approaches to create liveable cities. The learning activities will include lectures, field studies, and practical work in the design studio carried out during the five-day workshop. Before the workshop, during April and May, there will be preparatory activities carried out distantly by the participating students assisted by tutors at their institution as well as from other partner schools of the OIKONET network.

ARE YOU A STUDENT OF ARCHITECTURE FROM 3RD TO 5TH YEAR?
DO YOU HAVE A GOOD ACADEMIC RECORD?
DO YOU HAVE A GOOD KNOWLEDGE OF ENGLISH?

THEN YOU MAY PARTICIPATE IN THIS WORKSHOP
If you are interested in participating, please send us a short text describing the reasons why you would like to take part in the workshop to info@oikonet.org before **March 30, 2016**

Traveling and accommodation costs are covered by the program

For more information please visit the website oikonet.org or contact: info@oikonet.org
This project is funded with support from the European Commission (Project number 512604LFP2015125-EMASND). This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Figure 1. Belgrade workshop poster

3.1 Objectives

The workshop is aimed at examining strategies which embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies will integrate architectural, urban design and urban planning issues to create a multifaceted framework to develop liveable cities.

In the process to formulate these strategies it will be necessary:

- To undertake critical examination of different theories and experiences of planned urban transformations.
- To adopt a multi-sectoral approach (social, economic, environmental, cultural) with an emphasis on environmental challenges of adaptation to climate change.

- To identify the assets of the area to be revitalized – such as identity, memory and place – as well as the possible drivers in the local community and among local economic stakeholders that can be involved in the transformation process.

3.2 Case study

The area of study is a Kosančićev Venac, a historical part of the city of Belgrade. It is a heterogeneous, mixed-use area connecting the Sava riverfront with the main pedestrian zone, next to the Kalemegdan fortress. Despite its excellent position and evident potential for revitalization, this area has been deteriorating for decades, losing part of its inhabitants and failing to attract new ones. Its predominant use is residential, although there are many institutions of education and culture nearby. As unique heritage and a symbol of the whole city, its preservation is vital. In this context, the current situation in the Kosančićev Venac raises the following questions:

- What are the main reasons for the district not being vital and attractive?
- How can a sustainable development succeed to revitalize the historic centre Kosančićev Venac and reactivate its economic, physical, social and environmental structures?
- What measures are necessary to preserve its character and build on its existing assets (e.g. architectural and urban heritage)?
- In which ways might the procurement of new housing help to preserve social cohesion?
- Which types of housing are needed to revitalize the area while preserving its character?
- What challenges does adaptation to climate change pose with regard to the renovation of housing and urban structures and to the renewal of urban space?
- How does the connectivity with nearby areas and with the overall city need to be improved?

3.3 Learning Outcomes

At the end of the workshop students will be able to:

- Understand the differences between the various approaches to make cities liveable, such as regeneration, renewal and revitalization.
- Identify the specific characteristics of an area which embody a potential for future change.
- Develop a multi-dimensional analysis focusing on environmental, social and psychological aspects of liveable cities as a basis to propose redevelopment strategies
- Understand the importance of climate change as a driving factor to make cities more liveable, renewable and responsive to environmental challenges.
- Propose strategies to revitalise and regenerate cities which allow for the participation of local community representatives.
- Develop processes to transform existing physical structures for other purposes, to refurbish existing buildings, taking allowance of the underlying political and economic forces.

3.4 Program and learning activities

The learning activities will include lectures, field studies, and practical work in the design studio carried out during the five-day workshop. Before the workshop, during April and May, there will be preparatory activities carried out distantly by the participating students assisted by tutors at their institution as well as from other partner schools of the OIKONET network. The preparatory activities include:

- Providing examples of revitalization projects that address similar issues to the ones to be addressed in the case study in Belgrade.
- Getting acquainted with the different regeneration strategies such as renewal, revitalization, renovation and regeneration, among others.
- Understanding the historical, political, sociodemographic, urban and architectural conditions of the case study.
- Presenting a synthesis of the knowledge acquired in the preparatory activities in poster format.

3.5 Participants

58 students and 24 tutors from 17 Schools of Architecture and Urban Planning (one of them, from Russia), partners of the OIKONET network participated in the workshop. The participating organizations were:

- P1 LA SALLE- School of Architecture La Salle, Barcelona, Spain (Coordinator of WP 4 Pedagogical Activities) (3 students, 2 tutors)
- P2 ETSA-UPV- School of Architecture, Polytechnic University of Valencia, Spain (3 students, 1 tutor)
- P3 FASTU- Faculty of Architecture, Slovak Technical University, Bratislava, Slovakia (4 students, 2 tutors)
- P4 KUL- Faculty of Architecture, KU Leuven, Gent/Brussels, Belgium (4 students, 1 tutor)
- P5 BTU- Faculty of Architecture, Brandenburg Technical University, Cottbus, Germany (4 students, 1 tutor)
- P9 UTH- Department of Architecture - University of Thessaly, Volos, Greece (3 students, 1 tutor)
- P10 UKIM – Faculty of Architecture, University Ss. Cyril and Methodius, Macedonia (4 students, 1 tutor)
- P13 AAU- Department of Architecture, Design and Media Technology, University of Aalborg, Denmark (4 students, 1 tutor)
- P15 UCY- Faculty of Architecture, University of Cyprus, Cyprus (2 students, 1 tutor)
- P18 UGA- Institut d'Urbanisme de Grenoble, Université Grenoble Alpes, France (3 students, 1 tutor)
- P20 GTU- Faculty of Architecture, Gebze Technical University, Turkey (3 students, 1 tutor)
- P25 ISCTE- Department of Architecture and Urbanism, University Institute of Lisbon, Portugal (4 students, 1 tutor)
- P26 AF BELGRADE- Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, Serbia (5 students, 4 tutors)
- P27 BUT- Faculty of Architecture - Bialystok University of Technology, Poland (3 students, 1 tutor)
- P29 DIT- School of Architecture, Dublin Institute of Technology, Ireland (3 students, 1

tutor)

- P30 ITU- Faculty of Architecture, İstanbul Technical University, Turkey (2 students, 1 tutor)
- P31 VSUACE-Volgograd State University of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Russia (3 students, 1 tutor)

Besides, staff from P6- USI carried out the evaluation of the activities carried out before and during the workshop (see Appendix).

3.6 Workshop theme: “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating liveable cities”

Liveable cities provide physical, social, economic and political infrastructures that ensure their inhabitants evenly distributed wealth, affordable quality housing, healthcare, cultural infrastructures, quality education, environmental resilience and easy accessibility within the city and with other cities in the world. All of these goods and services should be provided for all the city population, avoiding disparities between classes and between urban areas. Providing a liveable environment helps to attract talent and investment which, in turn, secures economic growth. Being on the top list of the most liveable cities in the world is tantamount to prosperity and progress. Creating liveable cities is a collective task which involves all of the city’s stakeholders.

In the process of revitalizing cities, keeping a balance between the existing structures and the new developments is of major importance. The city provides the spatial milieu which accommodates and, at the same time, shapes everyday life. New ways of living coexist with traditional ones. The city is a multi-layered structure which carries the collective memory of the people. At the same time, it is an organism which needs new inputs to keep alive. Renewal, regeneration, reconstruction, restoration and redevelopment convey different balances between maintaining current spaces or creating new ones, between preserving or transforming the character of a place and, and between reusing existing structures constructing new ones.

Making our cities liveable involves adopting plans to revitalize existing urban areas. To this endeavour, improving existing built structures – buildings as well as public infrastructures – is not enough. It is also necessary to adopt strategies that intertwine environmental, social, psychological issues in the dynamics of renovation. Environmental issues include climate change over micro-climate, to urban green spaces and wild life. Social aspects span from economy and culture, over issues of gentrification and segregation, to the standard of living such as access to sports and leisure, schools and day care and elderly care. And psychological aspects range from a feeling of belonging, to the sense of orientation and the perception of safety. An interdisciplinary, inclusive and participative approach is necessary to develop strategies to achieve liveable cities that take into consideration physical, social and psychological realms.

3.7 Preparatory learning activities

The preparatory stage of the workshop started on April 2016, while it was built by teachers from March 2016. It was supported by a learning space specifically created for this purpose in **OIKODOMOS Workspaces**², following methodology applied in the previous two workshops.

The screenshot displays the OIKODOMOS WORKSPACES interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'User Name', 'Password', and 'Login' fields. Below this, the main content area is divided into two columns. The left column features a workspace titled 'Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating liveable cities' for the 'BELGRADE WORKSHOP' (June 6-11, 2016). It includes a description of the workshop's focus on creating liveable cities, a list of participating institutions, and a 'Bulletin Board' with news updates and student announcements. The right column contains a 'Bulletin Board' with news updates and student announcements.

Figure 2. Workspace supporting the workshop preparatory activities

From the experience gained in the preparatory activities of the previous two workshops in Cottbus and Lisbon, it became evident that the amount of tasks should be reduced and the structure of the learning activities simplified as much as possible, considering the little time that students and tutors could allocate to these activities due to the workload of their regular courses. The design of the preparatory activities was led by La Salle, with the support of staff from AAU, ITU and UTH.

The activities were structured in the following way:

- **LA: ANALYSIS OF PROJECT SITE IN BELGRADE.** This learning activity allows students and teachers to get familiar with the sites chosen for the workshop in Belgrade.

- **TK: Urban and architectural context analysis.** To carry out a functional, structural and morphological analysis of the site based on the provided maps and drawings and the reading the reference documents. To identify the issues to be addressed and the potential strategies to revitalize the area.

² <http://www.oikodomos.org/workspaces/index.php/workshops/preview/31>

Figure 3. An example of the site analysis done by the students from BUT

Accessibility

Figure 4. An example of the site analysis done by the students from UTH

Figure 5. An example of the site analysis done by the students from LA SALLE

- **LA: THEMATIC REFLECTIONS.** This learning activity introduced students to different urban regeneration strategies such as renewal, revitalization, renovation and regeneration, among others.

- **TK: Reading references.** To read some of the reference texts with the purpose of understanding the basic ideas behind urban regeneration and revitalization processes: motivation, goals and strategies.

- **TK: Providing examples.** To identify examples of urban revitalization/regeneration strategies on your own home town or country. To describe the examples taking into account the findings of previous tasks.

Figure 6. A case of urban regeneration provided by the students from ETSÀ-UPV

EXAMPLES OF URBAN RENEWAL IN BERLIN.

THE KOSANČIJEV VENAC AREA HAS THE POTENTIAL TO BE A FOCAL POINT IN THE CITY AND IT IS HARD TO UNDERSTAND HOW IT HAS STAYED DORMANT FOR SO LONG. DESPITE ITS EXCELLENT POSITION AND EVIDENT POTENTIAL FOR REVITALIZATION, THIS AREA HAS BEEN DETERIORATING FOR DECADES, LOSING PART OF ITS INHABITANTS AND FAILING TO ATTRACT NEW ONES.

WHEN LOOKING AT THE WATERFRONT OF KOSANČIJEV VENAC YOU SEE A LOT OF POTENTIAL FOR CONVERSION. THE SPACE, WHICH COVERS AROUND 0.23 KM², CONSISTS OF RAILWAYS AND OLD INDUSTRIAL FACILITIES.

ARE THERE EXAMPLES IN OTHER PARTS OF THE WORLD WHERE REVITALIZATION TOOK PLACE?

MEDIASPREE
LEGAL FORM: MEDIASPREE IS MERELY A LABEL. THE PLANNING FOR INDIVIDUAL BUILDING PROJECTS LIES WITH PROPERTY OWNERS, INVESTORS, AND THE BUILDING AREA: 1.2 KM². PROJECTUAL STARTED IN THE MID 90'S.
ITS VISION: A DYNAMIC WATERFRONT COMMUNITY WITH SPACES FOR LIVING, WORKING AND ENTERTAINMENT. MANY LISTED FACTORY BUILDINGS WERE INTEGRATED IN THE URBAN LIFE. THE AIM HAS BEEN TO CREATE A MIXED LANDUSE.
UNIVERSAL RECORDS, NATV. CLUBS, MERCEDES BENZ ARENA, COCA COLA, ZALANDO, SHOPPING CENTERS, HOTELS, OFFICES, HOUSING, CAR PARK BUILDINGS.

SPREEFELD
LEGAL FORM: NON-PROFIT CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATION, COOPERATIVE
AREA: 700,000 M²
PROJECT YEAR: 2012
ITS MISSION TO HARNESS ITS LOCATION'S UNIQUE POTENTIAL TO CREATE A SOCIALLY JUST, ECONOMICALLY STABLE, AND ENVIRONMENTALLY RESPONSIBLE URBAN BUILDING BLOCK.
ECOLOGICAL (PASSIVE BUILDINGS STANDARD) THE BUILDING COMPLY WITH THE MICRO-ROBOT-GARDENS AND PRODUCE THEIR OWN RESERVING ENERGY THROUGH A COST-EFFICIENT, A BIO-THERMAL SYSTEM AND PHOTOVOLTAICS. MULTIGENERATIONAL AND MULTICULTURAL RESIDENTIAL POPULATION
APARTMENTS ARE BARRIO-DEI
THERE IS COMMUNITY USE OF LAUNDRY ROOMS, FITNESS ROOMS, GUEST ROOMS, ROOFTOP TERRACES, AND THE MUSIC AND YOGA ROOM SELF-HELP DURING THE CONSTRUCTION
IN EXCHANGE FOR THE REQUIRED DAILY CAPITAL, USER COULD CARRY OUT AND TO CONSTRUCT OR WORK WITH IN THEIR DWELLINGS ON-THE-SPOT.
LONG-TERM AFFORDABLE RENTIS
RENTALS SHOULD AND CAPAT AT A LEVEL EQUAL TO GOVERNMENT SUBSIDIZED HOUSING.
THE PROJECTS ALLOWS MORE PEOPLE TO HAVE A SAY THAN JUST THE "EXPERTS".

URBAN RENEWAL...

...BUT FOR WHOM?

Figure 7. A case of urban regeneration provided by the students from BTU

- LA: COMMUNICATING FINDINGS: This learning activity consists in summarizing the work process and the findings on the previous proposed tasks and communicating them to peer

- **TK: Group presentation: Pre-workshop activities.** Each group of students participating in the Belgrade workshop had to upload a Powerpoint file accompanying the 10-minute presentation they will make on the first day of the workshop. The presentation had to communicate to the other participants the outcomes of the preparatory activities carried out in the Workspace.

Besides, each group of students at each participating institution summarized the work done in a poster. The posters were displayed in an exhibition at the Faculty of Architecture, in Belgrade, at the start of the workshop. They were thematically organized in three groups:

- A group of posters mainly oriented to knowing more about the assigned site – Kosančićev Venac (Figure 8)
- A group of posters giving more theoretical insights into the problems of revitalization and renewal (Figure 9)
- A group of posters which contained successful local examples that might serve as a reference for the case study in Belgrade (Figure 10)

Figure 8. Preparatory stage results – Posters focusing mainly on examining Kosančićev Venac

Figure 9. Preparatory stage results – Posters focusing on theoretical aspects

Figure 10. Preparatory stage results – Posters focusing on local examples of regeneration areas

3.8 Organization

The teaching methodology was based on a combination of lectures, field studies, excursions and practical work (design studio). Students were organized into teams, each one composed of students from different schools to strengthen the cross-country, cultural and educational exchanges. Each team was tutored by teachers from different institutions.

TEAMS

Group 1	<p>Júlia Marbà (LA SALLE)</p> <p>Antonije Levičanić (FASTU)</p> <p>Tonia Dalle (KUL)</p> <p>Wassily Walter (BTU)</p> <p>Efthymia Vrouza (UTH)</p>	<p>Teachers:</p> <p>Tomas Ooms (KUL)</p> <p>Carla Sentieri (ETSA-UPV)</p>
Group 2	<p>Naum Lazarevski (UKIM)</p> <p>Julie Pallesen (AAU)</p> <p>Marina Antoniou (UCY)</p> <p>Quentin Chaillet (UGA)</p> <p>Fatih Civi (GTU)</p>	<p>Teachers:</p> <p>Elina Krasilnikova (VSUACE)</p> <p>Ángel Martín (LA SALLE)</p>
Group 3	<p>Stefani Solarska (UKIM)</p> <p>Cheila Arruda (ISCTE)</p> <p>Michał Cychol (BUT)</p> <p>John Flynn (DIT)</p> <p>Ufuk Kucukyazici (ITU)</p>	<p>Teachers:</p> <p>Vasso Trova (UTH)</p> <p>Aleksander Asanowicz (BUT)</p>

Group 4	Vladislav Shapovalov (VSUACE) Ignacio Bartolome (LA SALLE) Lucia Bálintová (FASTU) Francesca Lysann Klute (BTU) Eirini Anastasiou (UTH)	Teachers: Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE) Sebnem Cakalogullari (GTU) Katrin Brünjes (BTU)
Group 5	Andrea Falk Pedersen (AAU) Gautier Hunout (UGA) Sarah Andrade (ISCTE) Martynas Bernecki (BUT) Gorkem Ertugrul (ITU) Matija Brković (AF BELGRADE) (tutor)	Teachers: Viera Jockova (FASTU) Jim Roche (DIT)
Group 6	Jaume Pla (LA SALLE) Rosaura Hernandez (KUL) Ilija Mircheski (UKIM) Sena Akgul (GTU) Andrew Mc Allister (DIT)	Teacher: Paulette Duarte (UGA)
Group 7	Adam Kubica (FASTU) Saeed Khoury (BTU) Anne Sofie Elgaard Sørensen (AAU) Alric Bonvallet (UGA) Denis Machado (ISCTE)	Teachers: Yasemine Alkiser (ITU) Nicolai Steinø (AAU)
Group 8	Wioletta Buczynska (BUT) Marina Strelka (VSUACE) Alexandre García Estellés (ETSA-UPV) Mara Usai (KUL) Mona Rahal (BTU) Igor Medarski (UKIM)	Teachers: Henrich Pfico (FASTU) Nadia Charalambous (UCY)
Group 9	Mimi True Sørensen (AAU)	Teacher:

Arzum Cetin (GTU)	Mihajlo Zinoski (UKIM)
Alberto Lopez de Lucas (ETSA-UPV)	
Zoi Hliadou (UTH)	
Teresa Mateus (ISCTE)	

Group 10	Javier Martí Isasi (ETSA-UPV)	Teacher:
	Marek Trebuła (FASTU)	Alexandra Paio (ISCTE)
	Dieter Michielsen (KUL)	
	Mikaella Raspa (UCY)	
	Sean Barrett (DIT)	

3.9 Activities program

The starting point of the Workshop was an informal socialization event on Belgrade Waterfront in a nearest proximity of the assigned site, on Sunday, June 5, 2016. After sharing works in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces and making contact in the Facebook group, for the majority of participating students this was first chance to meet face to face, as well as to identify their fellow colleagues and local tutors.

Figure 11. Gathering on the Belgrade Waterfront (Sunday, 5th of June)

3.9.1 MONDAY, 6 JUNE 2016

The event started with a short welcome and introduction words by the OIKONET project coordinator, Dr. Leandro Madrazo, and by Dr. Mirjana Devetaković, in representation of the host institution, AF_Belgrade. It was followed by introductions of all participating institutions in which teaching staff introduced their team members. Afterwards, the local tutors invited the team members to join them for refreshment in a local café and a short promenade on the assigned site.

Figure 12. Workshop official opening (Monday, 6th of June)

After a short break, the exhibition of the results of the preparatory stage was open, and each of the 16 groups presented their findings.

Figure 13. Exhibition and presentation of preparatory activities (Monday, 6th of June)

Figure 14. Students' groups from each institution presenting the results of the preparatory activities (Monday, 6th of June)

During the afternoon, participants visited the seat of the Belgrade Waterfront development where they received an explanation of the plans from the project directors, followed by questions and answers.

Figure 15. Meeting the representatives of the Belgrade Waterfront development company (Monday, 6th of June)

Even at this stage of the workshop, social media was already playing an important role, allowing participants to chronologically memorize each Workshop activity, as well as to share visual impressions and ideas.

Figure 16. The information collected on the site, shared within the Facebook group

3.9.2 TUESDAY, 7 June 2016

In the early morning, participants had a chance to meet representatives of the Belgrade City Government (Secretariat for Environmental Protection, Dr. Snježana Glumac and Dr. Miodrag Grujić) who presented the city plans to face climate change (Figure). Participants received printouts of the document “Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan and Vulnerability Assessment” both in Serbian and in English.

Figure 17. Introduction in the lecture on Belgrade climate change adaptation issues by Belgrade City Government representatives (Tuesday, 7th of June)

After this introductory lecture, the design work began. The teams of students were assigned a workspace in the room. Each of the teams was assigned a local tutor (e.g. a postgraduate students of AF_BELGRADE) which worked under the lead of the OIKONET teaching staff.

Figure 18. Studio space panorama (Tuesday, 7th of June)

The creative process within the groups started quickly, since the time for studio work was short-four days left until a final presentation of the results. The students came well equipped with their laptops and other design tools. AF Belgrade provided good Internet connection and overhead projector, free copy service for small formats (up to A3), and easy access to a nearby school café.

Figure 19. Working in the studio and preparing for an interim critique (Tuesday, 7th of June)

On Tuesday afternoon another lecture was organized in the design studio. Dr Aleksandar Videnović gave a short lecture on his experiences in designing a new multipurpose space in the highly protected area of Kosančićev Venac. A decision to organize the lecture in the studio space instead of the lecture hall was adopted for practical reasons: facilitating a less formal communication atmosphere for both the lecturer and the students, avoiding losing time changing places, letting the students refer to their own documents (sketches, photographs, maps, etc.) as they formulated questions to the guest lecturer. The same format was used for the lecture by Prof. Elina Krasilnikova, on Wednesday.

Figure 20. Lecture in the studio by Professor Aleksandar Videnović (Tuesday, 7th of June)

3.9.3 WEDNESDAY, 8 June 2016

An interim critique was scheduled for Wednesday, the third day of workshop, to review the status of the work of each individual group and to exchange ideas among all teams. The critique started after the lunch break and concluded late afternoon. The discussions were then followed up on the Facebook group where some teachers and students engaged in a fruitful exchange of ideas based on the review.

Figure 21. An interim critique in which the students presented their strategies for intervention on Kosančićev Venac (Wednesday, 8th of June)

Figure 22. Part of the interim critique was written down in the Facebook group (Wednesday, 8th of June)

3.9.4 THURSDAY, 9 June 2016

The fourth day of the workshop was entirely dedicated to finalizing the proposals according to comments received on the interim critique.

A TV report of the work done in the workshop was recorded during the afternoon. It lasted about three hours, including sequences from the exhibition space, studio space and scenes and interviews recorded on Kosančićev Venac.

Figure 23. Visit of the National Broadcasting Service to the studio space (Thursday, 9th of June)

3.9.5 FRIDAY, 10 June 2016

On the last day of the workshop, students prepared their digital presentations and finalized the posters then sent them to the printing centre. After the lunch break, students pinned up their posters and presented their final works in main lecture hall.

The presentation of final proposals was organized as a performance in which students acted external experts in charge of the development of the area, some of the tutors acted as international investors from their respective countries, and other tutors played the role of the City of Belgrade government. In the performance, representatives of the host institution acted the city government members: Dr Mirjana Devetaković, as the Major; Matija Brković, as the City Manager; Milan Varga, as the City Architect, and Milica Milošević, as the City Secretary for finances.

Figure 24. Final presentation – A performance simulating a dialogue between experts and city government representatives (Friday, 10th of June)

4 FINAL PROJECTS

Teachers evaluated the final submissions using a rubric based on the learning outcomes agreed at the beginning of the workshop. The comments were based on the presentations delivered in the final session. Afterwards, each teacher introduced the comments and the marks in OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

4.1 Group 1 – In Between

Group 1 oriented its strategy to improving public spaces on Kosančićev Venac, and proposed to create an online platform called “In Between” that will connect citizens, potential investors and municipality. The students describe its strategy as following:

WHAT IS “IN BETWEEN”?

1. In Between is a Platform for ideas and networks for quality public spaces interventions.
2. We envisage a cooperative planning and building culture.
3. Get involved to make the city (developing) the way you want.

HOW TO JOIN OUR PLATFORM?

Visit the platform at <http://toniadalle.wix.com/inbetween>.

Figure 25. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 1

Teachers commented and graded this work as following:

Comments and marks by Carla Sentieri:

The presentation was really good. The team members work co-operatively and the communicated the ideas in a visual media with many different resources. Just one advice: next time, try to show the platform and blogs in a slow manner. It was too fast. Congratulations for your work!

-Sentieri, Carla

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Paulette Duarte:

Congratulations for your work. This platform is a good idea and can answer to the demands of the cities which are interesting in participation in urban projects. However, we need more information about the use of this tool.

-Duarte, Paulette

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Yasemin Alkiser:

I like the idea of creating a platform, which might be virtual and/or physical. The next step could be focusing on different scenarios for different conditions. In my mind the most effective way of filling the gap in this platform is to create various scenarios and take measures. You can search the main aims of different stakeholders for physical environment. For example, all parties would like to spend less money but get more profits in this process. In your approach government refers to political aspect, citizens to socio-cultural and investors to financial. You can also specify professionals and academicians as designers of the platform referring to physical aspect. Different zonings should be decided how to be connect and how to be separated each other by specific functions. These functions can be attentive to be more flexible and movable and easily adaptable. One last remark is that now it is time to propose architectural design in the environment in different scale as architects, planners and designer. I think you have succeeded very well in a short time. Yasemin Alkiser-Bregger.

-Alkiser, Yasemin

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Alexandra Paio:

It was a very good strategy for the design process to create an interactive medium for collaboration and negotiation between citizens, municipality and investors. This will allow the practice to be continuum challenging on real-time processing. The Third Industrial Revolution introduces the architects to different ways of thinking and making. However, the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on the proposals was not so clear. It would be interesting to show an example how the platform works effectively. The communication process (poster, video and oral presentation) was good and clear.

-Paio, Alexandra

S	A	B	C	D	E
LO1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.2 Group 2 – Art / Urbanism

The purpose of this proposal was to make public spaces in the area attractive to citizens. They identified a series of spots which are amenable to renovation, and proposed some new functions to revitalize them.

Figure 26. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 2

Teachers commented and graded this work as following:

Comments and marks by Vasilija Trova:

You have focused on a specific program (art) to provide a distinct character to the area and you have proposed a series of themes to enrich this program. It seems as if that you have not spent enough energy to evaluate your proposals, to consider the difficulties of this project. With this respect you describe your intentions rather than a critical overview of the possible cons.

Team work presents certain difficulties but members should try to overcome them. In group presentations all members should definitely participate.

Comments and marks by Carla Sentieri:

There aren't references about the effectiveness of your strategy.

It would be interesting to have the macro scale of the problem (the structure of the city) and pass through the meso until the micro scale.

I have not been following your work as a team, and I can't evaluate the co-operative work.

Comments and marks by Alexander Asanowicz:

The interesting proposition - "Place of interventions" - places around which the local communities actions will be concentrated. But the proposal is concentrated on only one aspect of the revitalization actions.

-Trova, Vasilija

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

-Sentieri, Carla

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

-Asanowicz, Aleksander

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.3 Group 3 – Cultural Corridor

A cultural corridor was proposed, connecting different locations in the area with the transport network and infrastructure being part of the same path.

Figure 27. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 3

Teachers commented and graded this work as following:

Comments and marks by Angel Martin Cojo:

I would be concerned about the fact that a cultural corridor could be understood as a strategy oriented to new residents or tourism more than for the existing, local residents. It would be necessary to have a certain control of the proposed activities/ uses to avoid gentrification, for instance.

Marks by Mihajlo Zinoski

-Martin Cojo, Angel

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

-Zinoski, Mihajlo

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Marks by Elina Krasilnikova

-Krasilnikova, Elina

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Katrin Brünjes:

Implementing a cultural corridor and linking it to the existing school of arts is a plausible strategy to reactivate this part of the city. The idea of connection stays in a theoretical state. Deepening and describing the strategy to connect will support this proposal.

-Bruenjes, Katrin

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.4 Group 4 – Spreading Out

Figure 28. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 4

Teachers commented and graded this work as following:

Comments and marks by Vasilija Trova:

Nice ideas, good balance of elements to fuel the regeneration process, coherent description of phases.

What I have missed though is a thorough evaluation of the proposed strategies. Projecting our good intentions is not enough. We have to understand real constrains, social mobility, gentrification process, social inequalities and tensions to be able to test our nicely designed proposals.

Group work should be presented as group work. All members should have participated equally in the presentation

-Trova, Vasilija

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Alexandra Paio:

The group presented a very good analysis and design strategy. But the design proposals do not describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (citizens, municipality and other stakeholders). It is not clear the economic viability and social impact of the various scales of the project. The first presentation was clear and very good. The final presentation was not so clear.

-Paio, Alexandra

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Jim Roche:

The intention of this group is to upgrade key urban spaces in a hope that this will build connections and create a dynamic process that will grow and grow and make the area liveable. Good analysis of key areas. Library; open to residents, widen the path, keep the stones etc. You suggest limited and specific works to certain spaces. The treatments are well described in the sketches of existing and proposed though I struggle to understand the yellow treatment on the square. The big question is how to fund and sustain these works to the urban realm? The strategies rely too much on a faith in humanity. That is, upgrade an area and it will attract people. This may work but a more essential question is how to get more people living here. Since the area is partially abandoned and the population is elderly, it would have been good to have seen some proposals for getting new people and a social and age mix living in the area combined with this selected upgrading of the public areas. Good effort though.

-Roche, Jim

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.5 Group 5 – New Venac: Building for the Citizens

Figure 29. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 5

Comments and marks by Leandro Madrazo:

A series of places have been identified to be upgraded, both the public spaces (pavements, accesses) and buildings. However, there is not an overall strategy to intervene in the area over time, and the role of the different actors in the revitalization process are not mentioned. With the information provided it is not possible to know the objectives of the strategy and the expected impact. There is a diagram of the transport system at a city scale, but there is no explanation of its relationship with the proposed interventions at the lower scales.

Comments and marks by Katrin Brünjes:

Well observed analysis. Revitalizing the streets is one key element. Continuing the highway is to be doubted. Describing the different tools to revitalize will help to strengthen the proposal.

-Madrazo, Leandro

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

-Bruenjes, Katrin

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Paulette Duarte:

Congratulations on your work. You have very well presented your proposal. But some information about the policy of demolition could be welcome.

-Duarte, Paulette

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Yasemin Alkiser-Bregger:

Diminishing the traffic flow, preserving library ruins while creating public space and infill projects in the area are very good strategies. I also like the idea of reusing and reactivating strategies such as redesigning the cave. I would suggest you figure out how to reach the upper level of land. In this regard elevator or escalator getting through the cave. Highlighted pictures in red to show the problematic areas have made your graphic design striking. Now it is time to focus on practical and sustainable design alternatives for the hot spots that you specified. I think your effort is appreciable in terms of focusing on significant, practical and realistic approaches. Good job!

-Alkiser, Yasemin

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Carla Sentieri:

Congratulations on your work. You have analysed the problem from the macro scale to the micro scale. It would be good to describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals.

-Sentieri, Carla

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.6 Group 6 – Creative Hill

The group describes the proposal in the following terms: “The new art district focuses on unveiling the hidden gems of history and culture of Kosančićev Venac, to inspire and provide platforms for the local artists to showcase their work by composing a network of activities that will serve and engage the community, visitors and future investors. Our strategy is to connect the different places in the area through paths for pedestrians, as they descended through the main stairs and an elevator to the waterfront. The locations for our interventions aimed at providing spaces for local residents to embrace and for visitors to enjoy. Creative Hill will become a place for creativity, innovation and heritage, which is embraced by its community and shared with the rest of Belgrade.”

Figure 30. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 6

Teachers commented and graded the works as follows:

Comments and marks by Angel Martin Cojo:

I think this work shows a very professional and serious approach, very much taking advantage of the existing potentials of the area but identifying the weaknesses of it at the same time. Everything explained and presented in a detailed and clear way.

-Martin Cojo, Angel

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Vasilija Trova:

Key elements were nicely described and well presented. Presentation of ideas was coherent. The diagrams and sketches used were excellent. The description of the role of various actors was rather superficial, it was wishful thinking and projection of intentions rather than a test against real constrains. A nice / clever idea is not enough for an effective urban design proposal

-Trova, Vasilija

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Jim Roche:

Creating new connections. Good diagrams. Asking what Belgrade was and what it could become. Very clear analysis of the issues with good use of Sketchup model then clear descriptions of strategies responding to these issues using the medium of the aerial photograph. Excellent presentation all around both in terms of thoughtful strategies and representation. Good non-comital idea sketches for strategies of the different areas although some of these may not make much sense to locals or investors. They could be developed further of course. Phasing of proposals is not clear. %for art amount seems low - its 1% in Ireland? Seems to have been very good teamwork.

-Roche, Jim

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in a proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.7 Group 7 – Old Belgrade – New Life

The group described their proposal in these terms: “An alternative strategy to develop Belgrade’s public waterfront and local communities. The Old-New Kosančićev Venac’s main interest is to be: MORE accessible, green, diverse, sustainable, and identical”.

Figure 31. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 7

Teachers commented and marked the presented proposal by this group as follows:

The marks by Elina Krasilnikova:

-Krasilnikova, Elina

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Paulette Duarte:

Congratulations on your work. You could describe better the roles of the actors and the effectiveness of your strategy.

-Duarte, Paulette

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Yasemin Alkiser-Bregger:

You have collaboratively worked very well. Your presentation is very clear to explain what the main idea is in your project. Specifying three different zones is a very reasonable and effective strategy to understand and the different levels and make them connected physically and socially. Because public, semi-public and private zones all they need different approaches to develop them. Using various design principles of contemporary world such as open/green space, accessibility, density, sustainability, diversity and identity is a good idea to analyse, find out and adapt proper solutions in an historical area, Kosančićev Venac. Good job in such a short time and Congratulations! Yasemin Alkiser-Bregger.

-Alkiser, Yasemin

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.8 Group 8 – The Gaps

Students from explained their proposal in these terms: “The Gaps, it’s an urban revitalisation project that looks for a possible development in missed opportunities. A gap is an opening; a gap is an incomplete area. A gap is a difference between things, a disparity. For us, a gap is a lack, and therefore an opportunity. After identifying the gaps of Kosančićev Venac, both at the social and physical level, the aim of the project is to intervene through a strategy that step by step from a micro scale approach will lead to a general revitalisation of the area. Crucial point of the strategy is the role interpreted by the different agents and stakeholders, both from the public and the private sphere, which will concretely make the accomplishment of the strategy possible”

Figure 32. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 8

Teachers commented and graded the presented proposal by Group 8 as follows:

Marks by Mihajlo Zinoski:

-Zinoski, Mihajlo

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Vasilija Trova:

You are proposing a strong idea which intends to fill existing gaps with new programs for the community. But it seems that you fail to discuss the range of possible impacts that such a proposal could have. How are you going to avoid gentrification effects for example? It's important that we understand the consequences of urban interventions and not projecting our (good) intentions. Nice sketches and graphic presentation.

-Trova, Vasilija

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Karen Brünjes:

Linking the physical and social shortcomings of this part of the city and pointing out the opportunities for affordable housing is a valuable strategy. Structuring the proposal in several steps is logic. The transfer to your proposal is too subtle. Giving the implementation more emphasis would help your proposal.

-Bruenjes, Katrin

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.9 Group 9 – Sewing Belgrade

In this proposal, different issues were considered at three different scales:

MACRO

Connection with the other districts / areas:

Different morphology; Village inside a city; Different population, Diversity / Opposite / Contrasts between functions

MESO

Green infrastructure; Plot of the National Library; Lack of connected areas within the site; Excess of noise; Road too close to pedestrians

MICRO

Excess of vegetation – Lack of views; Lack of illumination; Visual pollution; Abandoned buildings

Figure 33. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 9

Teachers made the following comments on the final presentation of this group:

Comments and marks by Angel Martin Cojo:

The strategy presented here has the virtue of acting at different scales of intervention. The proposed actions are responses to specific architectural, urban or social problems, one by one, but without losing a general overview of the neighbourhood and the city.

-Martin Cojo, Angel

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Leandro Madrazo:

The proposal addresses the three scales, an analysis appropriate to each scale has been done. The proposed strategy intervenes at three stages, starting at the lower level (the river front), continuing with the sloped area and ending in the upper part of the neighbourhood. The different actors involved in each phase are identified, and the expected impacts shown. Both the analysis at the different scales and the strategy are clearly explained with graphics that are easy to understand. Nice live presentation, with a student playing the role of a planner convincing another student acting as a future dweller about the goodness of the proposal. Overall, excellent work.

-Madrazo, Leandro

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4.10 Group 10 – Markantno

The students described their proposal as following: “An Online Collaborative Platform based on the area of Kosančićev Venac. This platform provides a live view of our work and progress, and allows instant feedback on our design proposals and ideas on regeneration for the area”.

Figure 34. Poster and a web site submitted by Group 10

Teachers graded and commented the proposal as follows:

Comments and marks by Angel Martin Cojo:

It is a very good thing that this proposal deals with the issue of the roll of the architects in a contemporary urban changing situation, an important matter in an, each time more and more, inclusive society. Another positive aspect of the submitted work is that by creating a network of relations in between neighbours and making it visible, new investments in the area probably will feel more confident and supported in their economic initiatives.

-Martin Cojo, Angel

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Marks by Mihajlo Zinoski

-Zinoski, Mihajlo

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Leandro Madrazo:

The proposed is strategy is based on small scale interventions which seek to activate the public spaces to make them appealing to the people. Through the small interventions it is expected to revitalize the whole area, to recover the spaces the people. Citizens have been approached during the workshop, an excellent initiative to know their views about the proposed plans. The sketches and photomontages give some idea of the small scale interventions. However, there is no consideration of the relationships between public spaces and buildings. For example, in which way the renewal of a public space could lead to the upgrading of the surrounding buildings, or vice versa. Moreover, there is not so much consideration for other scales, beyond the small scale of the proposed interventions. There is an expectation to activate the community around the platform, but there is no indication about the ways in which the inputs from the citizens would be integrated in a design and planning process.

-Madrazo, Leandro

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Comments and marks by Jim Roche:

Interviews were a very good idea to get to know the residents' needs / desires and they obviously confirmed some of your own observations of the issues of this area of Belgrade. Good that you are building on the pre-workshop study done by the Leuven group on the creation of a digital platform which appears to be a very interactive medium for collaboration and consultation. Platform gives possibility for all potential stakeholders to react that could, if successful and if adopted elsewhere, create a new paradigm for physical interventions in the urban environment. Somewhat idealistic of course but it is good that the students dream of a more collaborative future especially on such crucial issues that affect society. The key issue is how would this be sustained? Who would spend the time on it? Will it continue after the workshop? They would need to be remunerated at some stage. Interesting but minimal interventions from the urban to the detailed level along the main street and reasonably well illustrated for the short time involved. The mix of detailed plan studies and 3-d sketches or

-Roche, Jim

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

photoshoped photos works reasonably well. The section should have been drawn better especially since you had the base drawing. Multiple studies are impressive with a good range of issues reviewed. Was any research done on decision to make the main coast road one-way? How would that effect traffic flows elsewhere? A good mix of research and strategies for revitalising the area, though perhaps more could have been included. Posters, Power Point and oral presentation was good and very clear. It is impressive that you returned to some of the interviewees and asked them about your proposals - a public endorsement of your work!

Comments and marks by Carla Sentieri:

I think it would be useful to have a macro vision of the problem that it isn't in the presentation. The focus is only in the area and probably to have a global vision of the city could be interesting. Congratulations on the work!

-Sentieri, Carla

S		A	B	C	D	E
LO1	Communicate orally their proposals in an proper way	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO2	Work co-operatively with team members to complete the work required (level of involvement of all team members)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO3	Communicate the ideas making an effective use of visual media in various formats	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO4	Describe the roles of various actors in the development of the proposals (participation of citizens in the development and implementation of actions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO5	Discuss the impact of multiple dimensions and scales on their proposals (evidences of a systemic approach to the problem)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO6	Evaluate the effectiveness of their strategy (effectivity, economic viability, social impact, sustainability, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
LO7	Describing the key elements of the problem	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5 DISSEMINATION

The dissemination of the workshop was carried out at the different stages -before, during and after the workshop- using a variety of media.

5.1 Facebook group

A Facebook group was started two months before the workshop to inform students about the preparations and begin to build a sense of community among the participants. Through this channel, participants received practical information regarding accommodation, public transport, money exchange, etc. They were also informed about the progress of the onsite exhibition. All posters summarizing the work of the preparatory activities were posted in Facebook in a sort of virtual exhibition. During the workshop itself, the Facebook group become the main communication channel.

Figure 35. Facebook group Belgrade workshop.

Figure 36. The Facebook group used to inform participants about the workshop preparations in Belgrade (Saturday, 4th of June)

5.2 Blog

The **workshop blog**³ is one of the standard dissemination channels used in the OIKONET project. It contains information about the program, objectives, participants and working groups. The work presented by student at the interim review and the final presentation are posted in the blog.

³ <http://oikonet-belgradeworkshop.blogspot.es>

OIKONET BLOGS

Lifelong Learning Programme

BELGRADE WORKSHOP 6 – 11 JUNE 2016

Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Liveable Cities
 FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE, UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE, SERBIA

HOME | TIMETABLE | PROGRAM | POSTER | GROUPS

INTERIM WORK | FINAL PRESENTATIONS

THIRD INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP

The third OIKONET international workshop will take place at the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade, from 6th to 11th of June 2016. This workshop will be dedicated to examining strategies that embrace the multiple dimensions, scales and actors involved in the process of creating liveable cities. These strategies will integrate architectural, urban design and urban planning issues to create a multifaceted framework to develop liveable cities.

KOSANČIĆEV VENAC

The area of study is a Kosančićev Venac, a historical part of the city of Belgrade. It is a heterogeneous, mixed-use area connecting the Sava riverfront with the main pedestrian zone, next to the Kalemegdan fortress. Despite its excellent position and evident potential for revitalization, this area has been deteriorating for decades, losing part of its inhabitants and failing to attract new ones. Its predominant use is residential, although there are many institutions of education and culture nearby.

The workshop will provide a learning environment in which students and faculty members from schools of architecture from different countries in Europe will discuss a variety of approaches to create liveable cities. The learning activities will include lectures, field studies, and practical work in the design studio carried out during the five-day workshop. Before the workshop, during April and May, there will be preparatory activities carried out distantly by the participating students assisted by tutors at their institution as well as from other partner schools of the OIKONET network.

Liveable cities provide physical, social, economic and political infrastructures that ensure their inhabitants evenly distributed wealth, affordable quality housing, healthcare, cultural infrastructures, quality education, environmental resilience and easy accessibility within the city and with other cities in the world. All of these goods and services should be evenly provided among the city population.

FACEBOOK GROUP
 • Click to access

OIKONET WORKSHOPS

- OIKONET - COTTBUS WORKSHOP 2015
Group 10: Proposal Description
- OIKONET - LISBON WORKSHOP 2014
ADAPTABLE LIVING - PLANS AND SECTION

COMMENTS
 Get this Recent Comments Widget

Tweets by @OikonetOrg

Oikonet @OikonetOrg
 Una vecina reasajada en los nuevos bloques de #militanovia comparte con #prohabil su experiencia

Figure 37. OIKONET Belgrade workshop blog

Finally, during the weeks after the workshop, the blog editors uploaded the final student submissions, one or two posters per group with a brief description.

Figure38. Final submission by Group 10 posted in the workshop blog

5.3 Twitter channel

From the first to the last day of the workshop, the activities were disseminated through the OIKONET Twitter channel.

Figure 39. Posts of the last presentation in Twitter

5.4 Presentation in the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad

The results of the workshop, in the form of posters, were displayed in the main Amphitheatre of the School of Architecture during the final presentation on the last day. After that, the posters were moved to the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad.

Figure 40. Announcement of the OIKONET Belgrade Workshop promotion in the European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad

Although it had been announced a couple days in advance, the public presentation of the project did not attract a large audience, particularly not the interest groups which, at the same time, were very active in criticizing the ongoing mega-development “Belgrade on Water”. It, however, did attract the Eagle Hills Company, developing “Belgrade on Water”, who’s representative was one of few participants of this presentation.

Figure 41. Introduction and students’ presentations in European Centre for Culture and Debate Grad

5.5 TV report on the Serbian National Broadcasting Service

A 4-minute report has been recorded by main Serbian National TV and screened in the TV Show “Žikina šarenica“, broadcasted both in Serbia and globally via RTS satellite programme⁴.

Figure 42. Images from the TV report

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rnKQQInVMIY>

The report was recorded on Thursday, the fourth day of the workshop. It included exterior sequences from the site, as well as the ones from design studio and the exhibition space. Prof. Leandro Madrazo introduced the project, Prof. Elina Krasilnikova gave her impressions on the Workshop and on the opportunity to visit Belgrade and to work in an international cooperative context, and the students from Spain, Belgium, Macedonia and Serbia were talking about their work. The report included segments in five European languages (English, the official language of the project, Serbian, Spanish, Macedonian and Russian) reflecting the sense of the Erasmus Life Long Learning Networking. The experience of preparing a scenario for an official TV report was new and exciting for both students and teachers, since it was necessary to prepare the material to showcase, the studio space in which the recording would happen and the short texts explaining the sense of the project.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Through the set of carefully chosen lectures, the students were exposed to a couple of different perspectives to the problem of upgrading liveability of the city through revitalization of the selected area of Kosančićev Venac. They had a chance to meet several stakeholders, citizens, city government representatives, project development managers, architects and academics. They spent an intensive week creating various solutions for revitalizing the area and making it more attractive and accessible, responsive to actual climate state of Belgrade, sustainable and able to respond to the challenging Belgrade Waterfront development. Besides, the participants had a chance to experience a week in the Serbian capital city, and to enjoy its beauty and hospitality.

7 APPENDIX: EVALUATION

The workshop was evaluated by students and tutors. A quality evaluation was carried out by Stefano Tardini and Anna Picco-Schwendener, from USI. At the end of the workshop the students in situ had the opportunity to respond a questionnaire. The tutors answered an online questionnaire. The feedback of tutors was collected through an online questionnaire (12 respondents). The results have been reported in Deliverable 6.3 – Evaluation of learning activities (see D6.3, Section 5).

7.1 Questionnaire

A paper questionnaire with 42 questions was handed out to the students participating in the Belgrade workshop in the afternoon of the last day of the workshop (Friday, June 10 2016), just before the presentation session. 43 students out of 53 answered the questionnaire and handed it back. This corresponds to a response rate of 81.1%.

The questionnaire was divided into the following four sections: A) Participant Information, B) Learning experience as a whole, C) Focus on pre-workshop activities, and D) Focus on actual workshop in Belgrade.

7.2 Participants information

Students from the 16 higher education institutions participating in the workshop in Belgrade answered the questionnaire. For each institution between 2 and 4 students answered the questionnaire.

The participating students come from 15 different nations, mainly from the same country as their institutions. Spain (6 students) and Turkey (5 students) were the most represented countries, as each of them had two participating institutions. 3 institutions brought both Master and Bachelor students, whereas 7 brought only Bachelor students and 4 only Master students; one institution brought 2 PhD students. In total 24 participants (55.8%) were Bachelor students and 16 (37.2%) were Master students; of the remaining 3 respondents, 1 was a MA graduate and 2 were PhD students.

Table 1. Number of students who answered the questionnaire by institution

Slightly more male (23, 53.5%) than female students (20, 46.5%) answered the questionnaire. As far as language is concerned, a majority of students stated that they have a good (55.8%) or very good (27.9%) level of English, while 4 respondents (9.3%) declared to be native English speakers. Only 3 respondents (7.0%) stated to have a basic knowledge of the English language.

7.3 Learning experience as a whole

7.3.1 Students' expectations

39 students described their expectations towards the pre-workshop and workshop activities. They can be grouped around two main areas:

- **“Social” expectations:** students expected to **live a social experience:** having a (unique) social experience (mentioned by 4), meeting new people from different countries and cultures (mentioned by 13), making new friends (2).
- **“Learning” expectations:** students expected to learn something new, especially in two main areas: communication and interaction, and architecture and urban design. More specifically, students mentioned that they expected to **work in groups, communicate and cooperate with other students** (mentioned by 9 students); the **international and intercultural dimension** has been mentioned several times, both in terms of learning from teachers and students from different countries and cultures (mentioned by 9), and learning about different (also professional) cultures (mentioned by 7). Several students mentioned specific subjects they expected to learn about, such as **urbanism, urban planning, architecture, liveable cities, regeneration and revitalization strategies, strategies for city development**, etc. (8 students). Several other students mentioned the expectations to learn something related to the **local situation**, such as the Serbian history and architecture, the architecture of Belgrade, the city problems of Belgrade and their possible solutions, and so on (mentioned by 6). Finally, it is worth mentioning that the expectations of some students were about **innovations in the way of thinking, working, studying architecture:** knowing different ways of facing architecture, learning different ways of thinking and of working, getting a new approach to studying architecture, etc. (mentioned by 5).

Almost **80% of the respondents** stated that their expectations **were fully met (60.5%)** or that they **had even been exceeded (18.6%)**. 20.9% of the respondents declared that their expectations were somewhat met, while **no one declared that his/her expectations were only partially met**.

Several comments in this section show enthusiasm and support the positive remarks about the learning experience, the exchanges between students, the workshop contents, the support from tutors, and the quality of outputs. A few comments highlight problematic aspects of the workshop, such as the effectiveness of communications and of group works, and the very intensive and tight schedule.

7.3.1 Learning outcomes & most important learnings

When asked whether they **the competences or learning outcomes** to be gained from participating in this learning experience had been clear from the beginning of the project, **most students agreed (58.5%) or fully agreed (29.3%)**. Only 5 respondents (12.2%) disagreed (4) or fully disagreed (1). This shows a considerable improvement, if compared to the previous workshops.

The following six **learning outcomes** had been defined before the start of the Pre-Workshop activities:

1. Being able to understand the differences between various approaches to make cities liveable, such as regeneration, renewal and revitalization.
2. Being able to identify the specific characteristics of an area, which embodies a potential for future change.
3. Being able to develop a multi-dimensional analysis focusing on environmental, social and psychological aspects of liveable cities.
4. Being able to understand the importance of climate change as a driving factor to make cities more liveable, renewable and responsive to environmental challenges.
5. Being able to propose strategies to revitalise and regenerate cities, which allow for the participation of local community representatives.
6. Being able to co-operate with team members, communicate my ideas and present them to others making an effective use of visual media.
7. Students were asked how well they felt they had achieved these learning outcomes. As seen from the graph below, they felt they had achieved most of the learning outcomes well; only the fourth one (“Being able to understand the importance of climate change as a driving factor to make cities more liveable, renewable and responsive to environmental challenges”) did get slightly lower scores. Two respondents explained in the comments that in the workshop climate change was not treated (1) and was not really a big topic (1).

When asked about the **most important or interesting learning aspect** of the whole workshop, students gave very different types of answers. Several students mentioned learnings related to **working in groups**: cooperating and working in groups with students from different countries and cultures (mentioned by 9), presenting and transmitting concepts and ideas (4) and English speaking skills (2). Other students mentioned having learnt **new approaches or new ways of thinking** (8): considering different aspects and perspectives (social, economic, cultural), developing new ways of thinking to be used also in the future and finding new strategies, etc. Few students mentioned the acquisition of how to use **new tools or software** (4), like Photoshop or the collaborative online platform. Finally, some students indicated aspects specifically related to the **local situation and culture** (7), like the Serbian culture, the values of Kosančićev Venac, and so on.

As for the use of digital tools during the learning experience, results are very similar to the workshop of last year: the most used tools were clearly **Google Maps, Earth, Street View and similar** (97.6% did a high or very high use of these tools), together with other Internet search tools and the Facebook group (80.5% high or very high). Only few students had a high or very high use of the **Workshop blog** (22.5%), probably because, as explained by one respondent, the workshop blog was useful as an information site but not as a working tool. Finally, more

than half of the students (56.1%) said they had used the **Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Liveable Cities”** with a high or very high frequency.

Almost all respondents (91.9%) considered that by using these tools they were able to access enough information to prepare for and work efficiently during the Belgrade workshop. The only remarks were about the access to computer workstations during the workshop (1 respondent), the stability of Wi-Fi connection (2), and the intuitiveness and the organization of the online Workspace and the website (2).

7.3.1 Comments and feedback on outputs of pre-workshop activities

Nearly half of the students (48.6%) received some comments on their pre-workshop outcomes online in the workspace, and 76.9% received some feedback after they presented their outputs on the first day of the workshop. In general, **comments have been appreciated**, as they allowed students to deepen and correct their thoughts on specific issues, to compare and contrast different case studies and to see different approaches, which they could then use in the following tasks. Only a few students found the comments not structured well enough, and – in some cases – not relevant to the topic. One student found that the comments they received were – sadly – not used enough.

7.3.2 Likes and dislikes

30 students wrote a comment about what they **liked** and 31 about **what could have been done differently**. The graph below shows how many times an argument was mentioned positively or negatively.

The **general concept** of the workshop was mentioned by 9 students as the thing they most appreciated and by 7 as something that could have been done differently: some students appreciated the contents of the activities, the structure of the program, the mixture of work and social events, and the distinction of the work into 7 tasks; others found that the program was not well-organized, that the purpose of the workshop was not very clear, that the workshop was too much oriented towards architecture, and that the objectives were too ambitious.

With regard to the workshop sessions, both the **teaching sessions** and the **presentation sessions** received positive and negative comments. Two students particularly appreciated the presentation sessions and the following discussions, because they helped them to develop their communication skills; four students found that two presentation sessions were too much, that these sessions were not well organized, and that the format of the final presentations was chaotic. As for the lectures, two students appreciated them, while two found that some teaching sessions were not useful, and that some lecturers were not motivated enough.

The **interactions and co-operation in the group works** were mentioned by 7 respondents as the most appreciated aspect of the workshop, while 2 thought it could be further improved: students positively mentioned the good co-operation among participants, the fact that 17 different schools were interacting together in one single place, and the possibility to work with other students and see their approaches and ideas. Two students found it difficult to work in their groups because there were students who were not able to work in groups and sometimes it was difficult to understand each other. As regards the **organization of groups**, 4 students particularly appreciated that students of the same countries were divided into different groups, so that heterogeneous groups were formed; on the other side, 5 respondents suggested to organize groups differently, e.g. dividing students by age or in a way that facilitates communications.

The **general organization of the workshop** was mentioned by 6 students as the most appreciated aspect and by 2 students as an aspect that could be improved. Four students particularly liked the **experience as a whole** and the **good atmosphere**.

Preparatory tasks and time management received only negative comments. Students would have appreciated to have more time to explore the city, and to work on their projects. Lack of time was also confirmed by the statement “I had enough time to do the work”, to which 61% of respondents disagreed or fully disagreed.

Furthermore, **the general experience of the workshop has been highly positive** for students: when asked whether their **learning experience as a whole** was positive, almost all students agreed (34.1%) or fully agreed (58.5%).

Moreover, **almost all students (97.3%) agree or fully agree that it would be worth repeating the learning experience in the future**, and some would even like to participate again.

7.4 Pre-workshop activities

Before the workshop in Belgrade, students were asked to carry out some preparatory activities in the online learning environment OIKODOMOS Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating Liveable Cities”. In this part of the questionnaire, students were asked questions about the **tasks** defined in the learning environment, the **materials** provided through it and the **training** received to use it efficiently. Furthermore, they were asked about their interaction with other students / teachers before the workshop.

7.4.1 Tasks in Workspace

85% of the students agreed that the tasks and learning activities proposed in the workspace were relevant and clear, 87.2% of them that the sequence of tasks and learning activities was meaningful to them, and 89.7% that the task-based structure of the workspace offered a coherent way of learning. The materials that were made available in the workspace were evaluated as useful by 92% of the respondents; however, only 50% of them claimed to have read most of the documents provided. In the comments, some students explained that some documents were too long, that they were too many, that the interface of the Workspace was bad, and that the documents in Serbian were useless to them.

In the comments, one student stated that tasks had the potential to create the information necessary to study during the workshop, and that they were important for creating the understanding of the study area and the subjects. Another student commented that the tasks were clear, but some resources (maps, drawings) could have been more comprehensible and in English. Another student claimed that s/he did not have time to study before the workshop. Finally, one student would have preferred to submit the tasks one by one, and not all at the end.

7.4.2 Training on Workspaces usage

87.2% of the students agreed that they received **enough training** to work efficiently with the learning environment of the workspace. Only one student stated that the workspace was not user friendly; another student complained because s/he would have preferred to have access to the workspace earlier than 10 days before the deadline.

Finally, 83.8% of the students thought **that interacting with other students / teachers** had been a good experience. Compared to the results of the preparatory activities for the 2015 workshop in Cottbus, this is a clear improvement (last year: 51%).

Students suggested improving interaction during the pre-workshop activities by:

- Anticipating the **creation of groups**: creating the groups before the workshop and asking them to realize something (mentioned by 5 respondents).
- Using other **tools to interact and communicate**, such as **Facebook** (mentioned by 3) and/or **Skype** (mentioned by 2).
- Letting **students introduce themselves** before the workshop, for instance through introduction videos (mentioned by 2).
- Other suggestions: promoting **surveys and participative decisions** (1), **creating expectations** (1), sharing useful **information about the city and about the tasks** (1), introducing **prizes and/or incentives** (1).

7.5 Workshop activities and feedback

In this last section, students were asked to provide specific feedback on the workshop in Belgrade and its activities.

7.5.1 Alignment of workshop activities / theme

Most students agreed that the **introduction and briefing sessions** were useful to make all aspects of the workshop clear (89.7%), and that it was clear **how the work would be assessed** (82.1%). With regard to the alignment of the proposed activities to the workshop theme, the **Studio activity** was considered very well aligned (92.5%), while the **Lectures** got a slightly lower results (79.5% of respondents agreed or fully agreed that the lectures were well aligned with the workshop theme).

In the comments, one student suggested having less verbal introductory sessions and more activities and events. Regarding the Studio activity, one student commented that the goals were clear, another one would have expected to also discuss concerns about housing issues, while the Studio mainly focused on urban design in general.

7.5.2 Usefulness of activities

As can be seen in the graph above, the two **site visits to Kosančićev Venac and Belgrade Waterfront were very much appreciated** by students: 94.9% respectively 89.7% of them agreed or fully agreed that the site visits helped their work during the workshop. This is confirmed also by some comments, where students describe the **visits as useful, inspirational, and as a very good experience**. One student suggested providing clearer and more specific prior information on what to focus on during the visit, in order not to miss important information. Another student would have preferred to do the visit in smaller groups and not together with all students.

Also the other activities were highly appreciated by students, even though to a slightly lower degree: 82.5% of the students considered the **tutoring sessions** as helpful for the design activity, while the two presentation sessions (preparatory activities on Monday and Interim critique on Wednesday) were considered as useful by respectively 87.2% and 82.5% of respondents. Some respondents highlighted that many presentations of the preparatory activities were similar, and contained repeated information, thus making the session a little boring. Regarding the Interim critique session, some students would have preferred having half a day more of working time instead of the session, which they did not consider very useful; furthermore, one student found that this session was scheduled too soon, when very little work had been developed.

7.5.3 Interactions and collaboration

Almost all students (95.1%) liked working together with students and teachers from other countries. Some students mentioned that this was **the most valuable and the best experience of the workshop**. Only one student stated that some participants were not willing to work.

85% of respondents considered the **social events** useful to break the ice and get to know each other; some students highlighted that that students themselves organized some social events spontaneously, up to the point that – according to one respondent – staying in the same hostel was the most important social event. Two other students would have preferred to have more social events.

Finally, 77.5% of respondents were able to **communicate effectively** with the other members of their group. This percentage is not very high, because the **language barrier** was still an issue for some students: 5 respondents commented that in their groups there were some students who were not able to communicate effectively in English. For one respondent, the difficulty was due to “interdisciplinary” communication: it was difficult for her/him, as an urban planner, to explain her/his urban point of view to architects.

7.5.4 Other aspects: free time, computing resources

Only 27.5% of respondents found that they had enough free time during the workshop: several students wished they had had more free time to visit the city (mentioned by 4).

Finally, 71.1% of the students considered the access **to computing resources** to be adequate. In the comments, three students mentioned problems with the internet connection and two complained that there were no computing resources at all.

7.5.5 Other comments

In the final comments, besides enthusiastic remarks and suggestions that have already been reported above, some further recommendations were proposed:

- Two students suggested having a longer workshop.
- One student would like to see where the work and proposals from the students finally end up.
- One student suggested opening the workshop only to graduate students.